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Terms and Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
AFC	Administrative and Financial Coordination
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMAP	Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme
API	Application Programming Interface
ARCO	Analysis Ready Cloud Optimized
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
DCAT	Data Catalog
DestinE	Destination Earth
DM	Data Manager
DTR	Data Type Registry
EAB	External Advisory Board
EBM	Executive Board Meeting
EC	European Commission
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EBT	Executive Board Team
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDO	FAIR Digital Objects
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GA	General Assembly
HE	Horizon Europe
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
IPR	Intellectual Property
LLM	Large Language Model
MS	Milestone
NIRD	Norwegian Research Data Archive
NL	Natural Language
NorESM	Norwegian Earth System Model
OFB	French Biodiversity Office
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
PC	Project Coordinator
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
RI	Research Infrastructure
RO	Research Objects
SDGs	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SSH	Social Science & Humanities
SSSOM	Simple Standardized Skos to Ontology Mappings
TL	Task Leaders
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leaders

Executive Summary

FAIR2Adapt enhances climate resilience by making climate data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), enabling policymakers and researchers to develop evidence-based adaptation strategies across Europe.

This document serves as the **project management handbook** for the **FAIR2Adapt** project. It provides essential information for the effective coordination and execution of the project, including an introduction to FAIR2Adapt, its objectives, and the rationale behind its approach.

The core of this document outlines the **project management structures, procedures, and key references**, including relevant details from the Grant Agreement (GA) and its annexes, the Consortium Agreement (CA), and additional decisions made within the Consortium.

FAIR2Adapt partners will use this handbook as a **reference guide** throughout the project's implementation. It aims to facilitate project management, monitor progress, and support efficient communication among partners and with the European Commission (EC). Additionally, it details the **collaboration and communication tools**, guidelines for organizing and managing meetings, and the requirements for ensuring the **timely and high-quality delivery of project outputs**.

1. Introduction

FAIR2Adapt is a European initiative aimed at increasing climate resilience by enhancing the availability and usability of climate data for adaptation planning. Through the application of FAIR principles, the project enables climate-related data to be more accessible, interoperable, and reusable, supporting the development of robust adaptation strategies across Europe.

The purpose of this handbook is to provide a comprehensive guide to the management and execution of the FAIR2Adapt project. It will serve as a reference document for all partners involved, detailing the project's scope, objectives, methodology, and management processes.

1.1. Scope

This handbook covers all aspects of project management for the FAIR2Adapt initiative, from strategic planning and coordination to practical procedures for communication,

collaboration, and reporting. It includes tools and guidelines for managing tasks, monitoring project progress, and ensuring quality delivery of project outputs.

1.2. Audience

The intended audience for this document includes all partners within the FAIR2Adapt consortium, as well as external stakeholders who may be involved in project oversight, communication, or reporting (e.g., European Commission representatives, advisory boards).

1.3. Structure

The document is structured into several sections to provide clarity and easy navigation:

- **Executive Summary** – Overview of the project and handbook's purpose.
- **Introduction** – Background and rationale for the project and handbook.
- **Project Summary Overview** – Details of the project's objectives, concept, and impact.
- **Project Management** – Information on organizational structures, management processes, and communication tools.
- **Knowledge Management and IPR** – Guidance on handling data, intellectual property, and innovation within the project.
- **Quality Assurance and Risk Management** – Procedures for ensuring high-quality outcomes and managing risks.
- **Annex** – Supplementary material and references.

2. Project Summary Overview

This section introduces the project, outlining its goals, methodology, impact, and how it is structured.

2.1. Overview

FAIR2Adapt aims to strengthen climate adaptation efforts across Europe by enhancing the accessibility, interoperability, and usability of climate adaptation-related data. By applying the principles of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) to climate data and knowledge, the project facilitates efficient knowledge sharing and resource integration. It empowers policymakers, researchers, and local communities to develop robust, science-

based, and context-specific climate adaptation strategies. The project builds on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to improve machine-assisted discovery and utilization of climate adaptation data, bridging the gaps between scientific knowledge, operational data, and practical, real-world adaptation needs. Through collaboration and data sharing across sectors, FAIR2Adapt supports the creation of comprehensive, equitable, and actionable climate resilience strategies for European regions and local authorities.

2.2. Project Objectives

The FAIR2Adapt project aims to improve climate resilience across Europe by enhancing the accessibility, usability, and interoperability of climate adaptation-related data. The project's main objectives are:

1) To improve the FAIRness of climate data across Europe:

FAIR2Adapt seeks to establish a comprehensive and sustainable framework for making climate adaptation data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). This includes developing and adopting community-specific metadata schemas, protocols, and standards tailored to Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) data and knowledge assets. The project aims to harmonize data access, ensure the usability of diverse data types (such as spatial, textual, and streaming data), and create actionable guidelines for data sharing, attribution, and licensing. These efforts will lead to the creation of machine-actionable data management plans and improved reusability of CCA-related data across the European Union. Through these efforts, FAIR2Adapt will promote open data practices, making FAIR and open data the norm in climate change adaptation research and policy.

2) To support the development of evidence-based adaptation strategies:

FAIR2Adapt will facilitate the development of scientifically sound, context-specific, and regionally tailored climate adaptation strategies. By enhancing the interoperability of climate data, including the integration of spatial data and other diverse data sources, the project will support decision-makers in accessing high-quality, harmonized information. Key achievements will include the development of services for data discovery, publication, and integration across multiple platforms and repositories. These services will ensure that local, regional, and national authorities can easily access relevant data for creating evidence-based climate adaptation plans, improving resilience to climate change impacts. Additionally, FAIR2Adapt will engage stakeholders across sectors and regions to build capacity for using FAIR data practices in developing climate adaptation strategies.

3) To create a collaborative platform for knowledge sharing among European stakeholders:

A core objective of FAIR2Adapt is to foster collaboration among various stakeholders involved in climate adaptation, including researchers, policymakers, regional authorities, and local communities. The project will provide a collaborative platform for seamless knowledge sharing and integration across different data environments, infrastructures, and stakeholders. By enhancing data interoperability and aligning different platforms with standards like INSPIRE and DestinE, FAIR2Adapt will create a framework for sharing knowledge across diverse scientific communities, ensuring that climate adaptation strategies are informed by a broad range of perspectives and expertise. This will involve engaging stakeholders in training programs to raise awareness and understanding of FAIR data principles, as well as providing customized tools to facilitate local and regional knowledge contributions.

4) To foster data interoperability and support data-driven decision-making for climate adaptation:

FAIR2Adapt will address the challenges of data fragmentation and siloing by enhancing the interoperability of climate data repositories, research infrastructures, and tools within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). By integrating spatial and non-spatial data sources and creating streamlined mechanisms for data access and sharing, the project will enable seamless interactions among different climate adaptation platforms and stakeholders. Key activities include the development of Natural Language (NL) querying services to improve user experience, the creation of common Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to exchange metadata and research objects, and the implementation of FAIR data publishing pipelines. These tools will make it easier for users to access and utilize CCA-related data, enabling data-driven decision-making that supports climate adaptation efforts across Europe.

2.3. Project Concept

FAIR2Adapt advocates for the adoption of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) as the foundation for creating an interoperable, distributed data ecosystem that empowers climate change adaptation (CCA) communities. By leveraging open standards such as nanopublications and Research Object Crates (RO-Crates), FDOs enable seamless integration, access, and manipulation of data in a machine-readable format. These objects, which include vital metadata, resource descriptions, and links to associated content, ensure that data and its context are preserved and accessible across a variety of digital systems and services. The

approach aligns with the vision outlined by Wittenburg and Strawn (2021)¹ in their paper "Revolutions Take Time", which advocates for progressively working towards creating a cohesive virtual environment, effectively forming “one virtual computer and one virtual data collection” from various resources. FDOs are transportable, lightweight, and flexible, allowing data to be easily activated and shared across platforms, ensuring compliance with privacy and security standards. They offer the freedom to operate without being locked into a particular technology, which is critical for facilitating the open exchange of knowledge. Technologies such as nanopublications and RO-Crates ensure that FDOs are flexible and adaptable, supporting the creation of interoperable tools that foster collaboration in CCA and beyond.

FAIR2Adapt’s goal is to enable CCA communities to integrate FAIR principles within their workflows, making data, information, and knowledge more accessible to a broad range of users, from experts to policymakers. Through the use of open initiatives like the I-ADOPT framework and the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies and Large Language Models (LLMs), FAIR2Adapt strengthens Europe’s interoperability efforts, offering scalable and fit-for-purpose solutions for climate adaptation.

2.4. Communities and Case studies

The **FAIR2Adapt** project is built around six case studies that drive the development of FAIR2Adapt's FAIR Supporting Resources. These case studies address real-world challenges and demonstrate the transformative power of FAIR data sharing to support climate action and the EU Mission on Adaptation. They foster collaboration across diverse stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, and communities, through training sessions, webinars, workshops, open forums, hackathons, and other interactive exchanges. Below are the six case studies in detail:

2.4.1. Case Study 1: NERSC - Spread of Radioactive Isotopes in the Arctic

Goals:

- Analyze climate predictions from the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM) under different Arctic scenarios.
- Assess changes in radionuclide distribution to evaluate the exposure risk to local populations.

¹ Wittenburg P, et al. (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/info12110472>

Challenges:

- Managing changes in sea ice patterns and permafrost thawing due to intensified warming.
- Increased radiological exposure from ²²²Rn exhalation.

Data Management Challenges: Climate predictions from NorESM are stored in the Norwegian Research Data Archive (NIRD) with minimal metadata, making it difficult for non-expert users to access and reuse the data effectively.

FAIR2Adapt Contribution: A framework to "FAIRify" climate model data, enabling better accessibility for environmental managers to define sustainable climate change adaptation (CCA) scenarios.

Key Stakeholders: Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP)

Mission signatories: Tromsø municipality, Troms & Finnmark County.

2.4.2. Case Study 2: IFREMER - RiOMar Project

Goals:

- Assess and anticipate coastal water quality and marine ecosystems under future climate impacts.
- Identify risks and vulnerabilities using RiOMar² model outputs to inform CCA strategies.

Challenges:

- Monitoring water quality in river-dominated margins.
- Supporting coastal businesses like oyster farming threatened by climate impacts.

Data Management Challenges:

- Stakeholders struggle with accessing high-resolution data from RiOMar and uncertainty in indicator computation for ecosystem vulnerability.
- Language barriers for French-speaking stakeholders.

² <https://riomar.lsce.ipsl.fr/>

FAIR2Adapt Contribution: FAIRification of RiOMar data to make it Analysis Ready Cloud Optimized (ARCO), enabling stakeholders to develop CCA strategies.

Key Stakeholders: French Biodiversity Office (OFB), Regional River Agencies, Coastal zone professionals (e.g., aquaculture).

Mission Signatories: La Rochelle Urban Community, Brittany Region.

2.4.3. Case Study 3: UHAM - Hamburg City

Goals:

- Investigate climate-induced stressors in urban societies.
- Integrate socio-economic data with physical climate hazard data to inform Hamburg's CCA strategies.

Challenges:

- Need for systematic, cross-sectoral adaptation across urban systems.
- Balancing adaptation and mitigation strategies (e.g., urban densification vs. climate stressors).

Data Management Challenges:

- Fine-scaled data on urban exposure and vulnerabilities is fragmented across different city authorities.
- Lack of updated, publicly accessible data on climate risks.

FAIR2Adapt Contribution: FAIRifying Hamburg's city data portal, enabling a more user-friendly and transparent platform for adaptation decision-making.

Key Stakeholders: Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg Senate Chancellery.

Mission Signatories: Hamburg City.

2.4.4. Case Study 4: FC.ID - FAIR-by-Design National Adaptation Hub

Goals:

- Develop FAIR and open data resources to design national adaptation hubs.

- Test the FAIR2Adapt approach in designing Portugal's first National Adaptation Hub.

Challenges:

- Growing pressure to build resilience against climate change at national and regional levels.
- Fragmentation of adaptation portals, causing confusion among users about credible information.

Data Management Challenges:

- Difficulty in extracting and curating climate and non-climate knowledge from various adaptation portals and platforms.

FAIR2Adapt Contribution: Creation of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) from relevant data sources, enabling connections between data and knowledge resources to support the adaptation planning cycle in Portugal.

Key Stakeholders: Governmental agencies, research centers, insurers, knowledge brokers in Portugal.

Mission Signatories: All Portuguese signatories (48 as of January 2024).

2.4.5. Case Study 5: SEI - Connectivity Hub and weADAPT

Goals:

- Improve the Connectivity Hub³ and weADAPT⁴ to support climate resilience communities.
- Promote collaboration, dialogue, and learning across different platforms and publications to reduce duplication and promote efficient resource use.

Challenges:

- Difficulty in finding climate resilience knowledge due to fragmented, siloed information.
- Lack of structured, discoverable resources.

Data Management Challenges:

³ <https://connectivity-hub.placard-network.eu/>

⁴ <https://weadapt.org/>

- Curating climate and socio-economic data from various platforms to inform CCA strategies.

FAIR2Adapt Contribution: Use of AI to construct taxonomies and knowledge graphs to enhance discoverability and support learning across communities.

Key Stakeholders: Knowledge producers, policymakers, governmental agencies, citizens.

Mission Signatories: Potentially all.

2.4.6. Case Study 6: ADELPHI - Climate Risk Assessments under the EU Taxonomy

Goals:

- Provide insights into climate risk assessments required for EU taxonomy reporting.
- Improve accessibility to key datasets used in climate risk analyses.

Challenges:

- Difficulty in harmonizing climate and hazard data across different EU regions.
- Businesses need to align their adaptation plans with local, regional, and national strategies.

Data Management Challenges:

- Data on climate hazards is not structured or tagged for easy discovery.
- Data access issues for businesses conducting climate risk assessments.

FAIR2Adapt Contribution: Making climate hazard data accessible and structured to facilitate harmonized climate risk assessments and adaptation planning.

Key Stakeholders: Businesses, consultants, governmental agencies.

Mission Signatories: European businesses and relevant stakeholders.

2.5. Methodology

The methodology will focus on the development and implementation of tools and processes for making climate data FAIR. This includes improving data access, establishing

interoperability standards, and developing user-friendly platforms that support decision-makers.

Technological Framework and Methodology

FAIR2Adapt's methodology emphasizes key technologies for implementing FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) to ensure seamless knowledge exchange across diverse ecosystems. By combining RO-Crates and nanopublications, the project forms a bridge for linking primary data (e.g., sensors, satellites, models, socio-economic data) to actionable adaptation policies. The collaborative platform, ROHub, developed within the RELIANCE EU project, will play a crucial role in managing and enriching RO-Crates within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Figure 1 provides a graphical overview of the FAIR2Adapt FDO methodology. Through the use of Data Type Registries (DTR), FAIR2Adapt ensures that (meta)data are semantically defined and machine-actionable. This allows for better interlinking of data types, ensuring the data can be understood and utilized across various systems and services. FAIR2Adapt will incorporate the EOSC DTR, advanced in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, to enhance the semantics of data, leveraging terminologies and external mappings through SSSOM (Simple Standardized SKOS to Ontology Mappings).

FAIR2Adapt utilises RO-Crate as an FDO implementation and exchange format for data produced and consumed by services in data-knowledge value chains. (Meta)data packaged as RO-Crate will conform to data type specifications available through the (EOSC) Data Type Registry. The list of data and knowledge providers on the figure, though not exhaustive, will be expanded based on user requirement elicitation.

Figure 1 FAIR2Adapt FDO methodology

Case studies will be used to validate the FDO framework, providing real-world examples of how FAIR and open data sharing can advance CCA strategies. By working with stakeholders in coastal management, urban resilience, and biodiversity protection, FAIR2Adapt will demonstrate the practical applications of FAIR principles in climate adaptation.

System Architecture and Implementation

FAIR2Adapt operates within a layered sociotechnical system, built around the "GFF

Hourglass model," which provides a flexible structure for data transformation and FAIRification. **Figure 2** shows a comprehensive overview of our open and extensible system architecture, which we will describe layer by layer.

Figure 2 Comprehensive and viable layered sociotechnical system architecture at the core of the FAIR2Adapt methodology towards a FAIR and open data framework for CCA.

At the top of the hourglass, raw data is processed through the FAIR2Adapt framework to become FAIR-ready, ensuring accessibility, persistence, and metadata alignment across various systems. The project ensures that data and metadata comply with widely recognized standards, including GEO DCAT⁵ for geospatial metadata, and facilitates interoperability through the use of standardized metadata schemas like WIS 2.0 and WIGOS.

The core of the FAIR2Adapt system is centered on RO-Crates and nanopublications, which act as the vehicle for research artefact exchange. Data and metadata packaged as RO-Crates conform to the specifications outlined by the EOSC Data Type Registry, ensuring interoperability and ease of integration with external platforms and services.

At the bottom of the hourglass, FAIR2Adapt will leverage services like ROHub and FAIR Connect to facilitate the discovery and access of FAIR Digital Objects. This integration ensures that stakeholders can easily find and interact with relevant data and resources, using services

⁵ https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/evolution/good-practice-library/geodcat-ap_en

such as the EarthQA engine for Earth observation datasets. The architecture is designed to be open and extensible, promoting the inclusion of additional services, tools, and platforms as the project evolves.

2.6. Consortium

The FAIR2Adapt consortium brings together 17 partners from 13 countries, pooling a wealth of skills and expertise to back the mission of climate change adaptation through FAIR and open data sharing. This multifaceted consortium includes service providers, technology professionals, scientific partners across varying fields, and 4 Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

Key players in the FAIR2Adapt project include:

- **SRL**, providing strategic input on e-infrastructure, drawing from their involvement with the Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration on Earth System Modelling Tools.
- **TIB**, known for their expertise in extracting and linking data insights and for leading the project's external communication, specifically the content maintenance of the project's website and social media channels
- **UPM**, bringing experience in FAIR assessments, paired with **GFF**'s adeptness at guiding communities on FAIR implementation.
- **Expert.ai**, contributing their experience from the RELIANCE EOSC project to strengthen the consortium's technical expertise in AI for processing scientific documents, extracting information, and providing multi-language support.
- **NKUA**, enhancing the project with AI and Earth observation data for climate change adaptation (CCA).
- **P4A**, offering expertise on spatial data and tools, particularly in relation to OGC standards, supported further by their affiliated entity **Lesprojekt**, which strengthens the project in this area.
- **PSNC**, playing a central role with their high-performance computing and cloud infrastructure capabilities, along with operational support to the EOSC EU Node, thanks to their success in EOSC Procurement Lot2 and Lot3. PSNC is also a member of the EOSC Interoperability Task Force, enhancing services with user customisation and infrastructure development.
- **DESCI** broadens the consortium's knowledge base in RO-Crate, enriching the project's capabilities to demonstrate interoperability across all phases.

Seven of our partners anchor the development and execution of our case studies, transfer cases and exploitation of the project results:

- **IFREMER** contributes ocean research expertise, supporting the RiOMar community with their deep industry ties.
- **NERSC** and **UHAM** bring their climate research expertise to the table.
- **FC.ID**, focusing on CCA decision-making, and **SEI**, contributing critical Social Science and Humanities (SSH) expertise and policy connections, reinforce the project's objectives.
- **FTC** and **ADELPHI**, both independent policy consultancies in CCA, bolster the project's commitment to delivering actionable, policy-relevant insights.
- **ALPHA** adds a strategic edge to the consortium by sharpening business models and strategies, playing a crucial role in non-scientific communication and paving the way for the commercialisation of project outcomes.

Together, the consortium partners form a robust and comprehensive team dedicated to advancing climate change adaptation efforts through the promotion of FAIR data principles and the collaborative sharing of open scientific data.

2.7. Impact

The impact of FAIR2Adapt is expected to be widespread, improving the availability and usability of climate data for adaptation across Europe. By enabling better access to high-quality data, the project aims to enhance policy development, improve resilience to climate change, and foster innovation in climate science and data management.

2.7.1. Impact from the Call Topic

FAIR2Adapt will develop a collaborative framework to accelerate climate change adaptation research, facilitating the creation of comprehensive and scientifically-sound climate adaptation strategies and plans. This initiative promises multifaceted benefits for stakeholders across Europe, including scientific advancement, economic resilience, social-environmental well-being, and responsive policy development.

Contributions Towards the Topic Outcomes and Destination Impacts:

- **Seamless interactions between EOSC, operational data spaces, researchers, and stakeholders:** FAIR2Adapt will implement a FAIRification framework, combining a community-driven approach, impact demonstration, and an adaptation hub blueprint. This framework ensures that data is discoverable, accessible, interoperable, and

reusable across key platforms, thus supporting evidence-based planning and decision-making at all levels.

- **Open and FAIR data as the new norm for research contributing to climate change adaptation:** FAIR2Adapt will act as a catalyst by developing guidelines and tools for FAIR data practices, including seamless integration with the EOSC ecosystem. The project will create a community-driven data ecosystem and revolutionize data accessibility through natural language search, empowering stakeholders to conduct robust, collaborative analysis on shared data and fostering the development of data-driven adaptation strategies.
- **EU-wide sharing of research data relevant to climate adaptation:** FAIR2Adapt will streamline data discovery, enhance EOSC's central role, and improve data interoperability. The project will integrate insights from regional and local communities and expand the sharing capabilities of existing knowledge platforms. By demonstrating the benefits of data sharing through success stories, the project will support various scales of adaptation initiatives across Europe.
- **EOSC as a trusted research and innovation platform supporting interdisciplinary research on climate adaptation:** The FAIR2Adapt framework will enhance the interoperability of EOSC's data, tools, and research infrastructures, streamlining data discovery and accessibility. This will attract interdisciplinary researchers, establish EOSC as the go-to platform for climate change adaptation research, and enable frictionless data exchange, fostering a knowledge-sharing network. Emphasizing community-based, real-world climate adaptation solutions will strengthen the practical impact of the Green Deal Data Space.
- **Contributing to the HE EOSC Partnership and other relevant partnerships related to climate adaptation:** FAIR2Adapt will prioritize inclusivity and long-term sustainability, enhancing interoperability within EOSC. By aligning with EOSC Partnership objectives, the project ensures lasting value for climate change adaptation research, inspires broader adoption, and reinforces the value proposition of the EOSC Partnership. FAIR2Adapt will also target collaborations with EU Mission-relevant initiatives.

2.7.2. Wider/Expected Impact

This section outlines both the short-term and long-term transformative effects that the FAIR2Adapt project aims to achieve in research, collaboration, data access, and trust in science, driving significant advancements in climate change adaptation and fostering cross-disciplinary cooperation.

Transforming Research Outputs:

- *Short-term*: Empower researchers and stakeholders to create, share, and utilize knowledge more effectively, leading to higher-quality research and enhanced innovation.
- *Long-term*: Champion FAIR principles, accelerate discovery, promote cross-disciplinary impact, support data-driven decision-making, and foster public/private collaboration and informed investment.

Facilitating Multi-disciplinary Cooperation:

- *Short-term*: Foster knowledge exchange across disciplines.
- *Long-term*: Promote novel discoveries and solutions by integrating diverse community perspectives and demonstrating the tangible impact of FAIR and open data on climate adaptation strategies.

Seamless Data Access and Management:

- *Short-term*: Establish a comprehensive and sustainable FAIR and open data framework for climate change adaptation, facilitating seamless data access and management.
- *Long-term*: Stimulate innovation, support sustainable ecosystems, and enhance decision-making processes.

Improving Trust in Science:

- *Short-term*: Advance FAIR principles in climate change adaptation research, support validation and reuse of research results, and communicate the merits of open science to the public.
- *Long-term*: Enable accountable and reproducible research, transparent knowledge exchange, multi-perspective validation, and accessible and traceable knowledge.

2.7.3. Impact for Society

FAIR2Adapt addresses the urgent threat of climate change by empowering communities, policymakers, researchers, and businesses with the knowledge and tools necessary to build climate resilience.

- **Strengthening the European Research Landscape**: FAIR2Adapt will bolster European research infrastructure by solidifying the EOSC ecosystem and promoting open access and interoperability of scientific data.

- **Fostering Informed & Effective Decision-Making:** The project will enable better-informed planning for governments, businesses, and communities, supporting scalable and cost-effective climate change adaptation strategies.
- **Empowering Resilient Communities:** By reflecting real-world needs and priorities in adaptation strategies, FAIR2Adapt will foster the development of effective climate adaptation plans at the community level.
- **Accelerating Innovation:** By promoting collaborative research and multidisciplinary approaches, FAIR2Adapt will unlock innovation for targeted climate adaptation solutions.
- **Stimulating a Climate-Smart Economy:** The project will fuel the development of new value-added services by the private sector, supporting economic resilience and climate adaptation.
- **Building Trust in Science:** Focusing on FAIR principles and data transparency, FAIR2Adapt will build public confidence in science-led solutions and empower individuals and organizations to make evidence-based decisions.

Through these pathways, FAIR2Adapt is set to make a transformative impact on climate change adaptation research, fostering a more resilient, informed, and adaptable Europe in the face of climate change.

3. Project Management

3.1. Implementation overview

The implementation of the FAIR2Adapt project is organized into a set of Work Packages (WPs) designed to achieve the project's main objectives. These work packages ensure a coherent and efficient approach to advancing climate change adaptation through FAIR data practices, open data sharing, and collaborative support. FAIR2Adapt's streamlined work plan is depicted in Figure 3.

WP1 - Project Management, Coordination, and Governance: project internal coordination, administrative, financial, quality, and risk management, management of the External Advisory Board, and liaison with the EC.

WP2 - Core FDO Infrastructure: standardisation for managing and exchanging data through FDOs; integration of technical results such as DTR-based data, RO-Crate profiles, updated

FAIROs⁶, geospatial search and discovery using NL questions, and the services for text analytics, data science, knowledge synthesis; operation and maintenance of the services and infrastructure.

WP3 - FDO-driven FAIRification Framework: Support the FAIRification of data and services for CCA communities.

WP4 - User-facing knowledge Services in Support for CCA: Provide user-centric services to help stakeholders search, find, and access FDOs.

WP5 - Community Support and Engagement: streamline the FAIR2Adapt user experience, through capacity building, training, and co-designing CCA tools.

WP6 - Case studies and end-user applications: test and validate the FAIR and open data sharing framework through real-world case studies that support regions, cities, and local authorities.

WP7 - Communication, Dissemination, Sustainability and Exploitation: Deliver and maintain a Communication, Marketing & Dissemination Plan and Strategy for a sustainable implementation strategy, and cooperate with EOOSC, the Mission adaptation, DestinE, the European Data Infrastructure, and other related initiatives and programmes, promoting further use of project results.

Figure 3 Schematic overview of main interactions between Work Packages

These work packages are interlinked to ensure an integrated approach, facilitating smooth data flows, community engagement, and the development of scalable solutions for climate adaptation. The successful execution of these work packages will ensure that the project meets its objectives, delivers tangible impact, and contributes to the broader landscape of climate adaptation research and action.

The table below summarizes the staff effort per participant for each Work Package.

⁶ <https://oeg-upm.github.io/FAIR-Research-Object/ro/>

D1.1 – Project Handbook

Table 1 Summary of staff effort

Partner	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	Total PMs
1. SRL	21	-	9	17	15	12	6	80
2. TIB	3	6	9	24	6	6	18	72
3. UPM	1	18	42	-	3	3	3	70
4. IFREMER	-	-	3	6	5	15	1	30
5. PSNC	1.5	40	6	10	8	-	7.5	73
6. ALPHA	3	-	-	5	8	12	50.29	78.29
7. Expert.ai	3	11	35	20	1	-	4	74
8. UHAM	-	-	-	-	6	11	1	18
9. FC.ID	3	-	-	12	12	32	8	67
10. SEI	1	-	-	8	9	15	6	39
11. P4A	1	5	15	12	9	-	2	44
12. NKUA	-	42	3	6	-	-	1	52
13. NERSC	-	-	-	-	6.5	7	0.5	14
14. GFF	1	4	6	3	18	3	3	38
15. FTC	2	-	-	1	5	8.5	11.5	28
16. ADELPHI	1	-	-	-	3	31	1	36
17. DESCI (CH)	1	8	8	18	-	-	1	36
18. LesProject (Third party)	-	6	9	4	-	-	2	21
Total PMs	42.5	140	145	146	114.5	155.5	126.79	870.29

The milestones (by date) in the FAIR2Adapt project are:

Table 2 Milestones (by date) in the FAIR2Adapt project

MS no.	Milestone name	WPs	Date	Means of verification
MS1.1	Project kick-off meeting	WP1	M1	Minutes approved by the partners.
MS7.1	FAIR2Adapt Branding	WP7	M1	Branding material available
MS1.2	External Advisory board is established	WP1	M2	All board members appointed and details available to the consortium.
MS5.1	FAIR Awareness course	WP5	M2	Nanopublications declaring the first delivery of the course along with nanopublications for the participation attendance.
MS5.2	Helpdesk Guide is publicly available online	WP5	M2	The GitHub repository is established in the FAIR2Adapt GitHub organization (https://github.com/FAIR2Adapt), and the Helpdesk Website is operational for assistance requests. Our user support strategy, resources, and feedback mechanisms are detailed online, with plans for continuous improvement based on user input.
MS7.2	FAIR2Adapt Web platform	WP7	M3	Website up and running

MS6.1	1 st set of FAIR2Adapt Case studies workshops	WP6	M3	Workshops agenda & summary, including number of participants are available online
MS3.1	FAIRification framework API specification	WP3	M6	1 st technical specification of the framework available online for comment. It defines common APIs for integrating all FAIR supporting services within.
MS5.3	FIPs	WP5	M6	FAIR Implementation Profiles published as nanopublications for all case studies from WP6.
MS5.4	SIPs	WP5	M6	Semantic Interoperability Profiles published as nanopublications for all case studies from WP6.
MS6.2	Case studies defined and started	WP6	M7	Case studies described on the FAIR2Adapt website
MS7.3	New Technical Working Group (TWG) on CCA data management is established	WP7	M8	Meeting agenda of the first meeting for the Mission Adaptation.
MS5.5	Community-specific metadata	WP5	M9	Community-specific metadata published and given to Task 2.1.
MS4.1	Draft specifications for Knowledge Services	WP4	M10	Draft technical specifications translating the user requirements (Task 5.2) into system specifications for Knowledge Services available online.
MS2.1	1 st set of RO-Crate profiles tailored to support the mission adaptation to CCA	WP2	M12	1 st set of RO-Crate profiles' specification is published online
MS2.2	Data and knowledge search and discovery service - version 1	WP2	M15	The 1 st release of the Data and knowledge search and discovery service is available on EOSC with its online documentation and test by project partners.
MS3.2	Alpha release of the FAIR Supporting Services	WP3	M15	1 st release of the FAIR supporting services (FDO-API, assessment, variable alignment, information extraction, FAIR data publishing) available and tested within the project.
MS4.2	Alpha release of Knowledge Services	WP4	M15	1 st release of Knowledge Services implementing the first specifications tested by the project partners.
MS2.3	FDO services integrated to ROHub - version 1	WP2	M18	1 st version released of ROHub with all the initial versions of FAIR2Adapt services & tested by case studies.
MS6.3	2 nd set of FAIR2Adapt Case studies workshops	WP6	M20	Workshop agendas & summary, including number of participants are available online.
MS4.3	Revised specifications for Knowledge Services	WP4	M21	Revised technical specifications that translate user requirements (Task 5.2) into system specifications for Knowledge Services available online.
MS3.3	Beta release of the FAIR supporting Services	WP3	M21	Online summary of the evaluation of the FAIR supporting services as part of the FAIRification framework based on the CCA case studies.
MS6.4	1 st meeting for future uptake of FAIR2Adapt via EU Mission	WP6	M21	First meeting agenda about uptake of FAIR2Adapt resources documented online.
MS2.4	2 nd set of RO-Crate profiles tailored to support the mission adaptation to CCA	WP2	M24	2 nd set of RO-Crate profiles' specification is published online
MS4.4	Beta release of Knowledge Services	WP4	M24	2 nd release of Knowledge Services implementing the revised specifications tested by the project partners

MS6.5	2 mission adaptation uptake transfer cases confirmed and started	WP6	M24	Agreement confirmed by document or email with short roadmap for the corresponding mission adaptation.
MS2.5	Data and knowledge search and discovery service - final version	WP2	M28	The final release of the Data and knowledge search and discovery service is available on EOSC with its online documentation.
MS3.4	Final release of the FAIR supporting Services	WP3	M28	Online summary of the evaluation of the FAIR supporting services as part of the FAIRification framework, based on the CCA case studies.
MS4.5	Final release of Knowledge Services	WP4	M28	3 rd release of Knowledge Services implementing all user feedback and validated by case studies.
MS2.6	FDO services integrated to Rohub - final version	WP2	M30	Final version released of ROHub with all the final releases of FAIR2Adapt services & tested by case studies.
MS2.7	Nanopublications describing FAIR Supporting Resources	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5	M30	All the FAIR Supporting Resources developed in the project like FIPs, metadata schemas, community vocabularies, customised services are described with FAIR metadata using nanopublications published in FAIR Connect.
MS4.6	Customisable dashboards	WP4	M30	Examples of customisable dashboards deployed are available online and has been validated by case studies.
MS5.6	Multi-stakeholder Open Forum	WP5	M33	Agenda with info on the selected themes (e.g. based on the Case studies), list of the CCA challenges brought by stakeholders and outcomes of the co-design CCA activities, including anonymized feedback, are summarised on the project website and published as nanopublications.
MS6.6	FAIR2Adapt Validation starts with transfer cases.	WP6	M33	An FDO was created for each transfer case and the selected transfer cases are documented on the project website.

3.2. Organizational structure and decision making

The FAIR2Adapt structure, as depicted in the **Figure 4**, comprises the Administrative and Financial Coordination (AFC) managed by Louise Bolands Eklund (SRL) who is responsible for the contractual interaction with the EC, and Project Coordinator (PC), Anne Fouilloux (SRL). The PC who reports to the Project Management Office (PMO), comprising one representative for each beneficiary, is the ultimate governing body of the project which validates the major project decisions. The PMO meets at Ordinary General Assemblies held (online) thrice yearly and can organise Extraordinary General Assemblies as needed. The Project Management Team (PMT), which includes AFC, PC, and Work Package Leaders (WPL), ensures project quality, controls finances and administration, strategizes dissemination, and handles conflict resolutions, among other duties. Daily project management is provided through regular calls led by the WPLs, with conflicts addressed according to the procedures outlined in the

Consortium Agreement. The Work Package Leaders are **Anne Fouilloux** (SRL) for WP1, **Raul Palma** (PSNC) for WP2, **Daniel Garijo** (UPM) for WP3, **Markus Stocker** (TIB) for WP4, **Barbara Magagna** (GFF) for WP5, **Tiago Capela Lourenço** for WP6, and **Claudia Maltoni** (ALPHA) for WP7. Each WPL is in charge of coordinating contributions to their WP. Their roles, responsibilities, voting schemes and veto rights are detailed in the Consortium Agreement.

Figure 4 FAIR2Adapt Organisational structure

- Task Leaders (TLs) are responsible for the technical follow-up of their specific tasks and for coordinating with other tasks within the Work Packages. They lead the preparation of deliverables resulting from their tasks, coordinate with other tasks to ensure their participation in deliverable preparation, and prepare and deliver internal task progress reports to the Work Package Leader (WPL).
- The General Assembly (GA) is the high-level management body of the project, chaired by the Project Manager. It is composed of one representative from each partner involved in the project and serves as the ultimate decision-making body of the Consortium. The GA is responsible for approving the management structure, project direction, and the Consortium Agreement.
- The Data Manager (DM) coordinates the project’s data management to ensure the usability, accountability, and quality of the data. This includes valorizing the data, either by using it for other market applications when possible and relevant or by making it open to the scientific community. The DM will be appointed by SRL.
- The External Advisory Board (EAB) offers strategic advice on the project’s direction and impact. Composed of senior experts, it helps address European priorities and connects with other initiatives. The EAB is composed of **Lorand Janos Szentannai** (Sigma2, Norway) and **Kati Mattern** (Expert – European Climate adaptation platform/Climate-ADAPT, European Environment Agency, Denmark). The EAB will meet annually (online), with additional meetings upon PMO request.

3.3. Collaboration and communication tools

Effective collaboration and communication tools are crucial for the successful execution of the FAIR2Adapt project. The project's internal communication is facilitated through secure digital platforms, granting each partner independent access to project documents, reports, meeting agendas, and other relevant materials. This section presents an overview of the various tools used, such as mailing lists, virtual meeting systems, the project website, collaborative workspaces, cloud storage services, version control systems, and task management trackers. These tools have already been selected to ensure efficient project operations. The following subsections provide a concise description of the key features of each tool.

3.3.1. Email & mailing lists

Email serves as the primary communication method for exchanging information among FAIR2Adapt Consortium members. To ensure better organization and tracking, consortium-related messages should preferably be sent through designated project mailing lists. These lists help manage targeted communication and maintain a record of sent emails.

Dedicated mailing lists have been established to streamline information exchange within specific activity groups. The mailing lists for the FAIR2Adapt project, managed by SRL, include:

- f2a-consortium@simula.no: General mailing list for all consortium members (excluding administrative members).
- f2a-wp2@simula.no, f2a-wp3@simula.no, f2a-wp4@simula.no, f2a-wp6@simula.no: Mailing lists dedicated to WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP6 members, respectively.

3.3.2. Logo & templates

The logos for the FAIR2Adapt project have been designed and can be used across all project documents, deliverables, and communication channels. Similarly, templates for project presentations and deliverables have been created and are ready for use. These logos and document templates are stored in the cloud file hosting system set up as a collaboration tool for the FAIR2Adapt project. The logos (available in various background options) and templates for deliverables and presentations can be accessed via the following links:

- Project logo: <https://w3id.org/ro-id/c8bd3371-151b-4650-9cb5-a64e40adf506/resources/0858f04d-2513-4c15-b0ea-a4fc0cea722b>

- Template for deliverables: <https://w3id.org/ro-id/c8bd3371-151b-4650-9cb5-a64e40adf506/resources/54bfedd3-5447-4d6a-bb5c-18c8f51c3404>
- Template for presentations: <https://w3id.org/ro-id/c8bd3371-151b-4650-9cb5-a64e40adf506/resources/73615167-a823-4994-bd44-8be352d465d7>

Figure 5 displays the FAIR2Adapt project logo, while Figures 6 and 7 show the templates.

Figure 5 FAIR2Adapt logo

Grant Agreement N° 101188256

Deliverable DX.Y
Title

Contractual delivery date: MZ
Actual delivery date: ...
Responsible partner: PXX - XX

Project Title	
Deliverable number	DX.Y
Deliverable title	Title
Author(s):	
Responsible Partner:	PX - XXX
Date:	
Nature	R
Distribution level (CO, PU):	PU

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Figure 6 FAIR2Adapt Deliverable template

Figure 7 FAIR2Adapt project presentation template

3.3.3. Video-conferencing system

Seamless communication is essential for the FAIR2Adapt consortium, given the remote collaboration among partners. To support this, a reliable online meeting platform is necessary for virtual discussions, video calls, and screen sharing. Zoom has been selected as the primary conferencing tool due to its user-friendly interface, flexibility, and accessibility across both desktop and mobile devices.

FAIR2Adapt has a Zoom service subscription managed by SRL, which can provide dedicated Zoom links for various meeting purposes when needed. However, for Work Package meetings or other task force discussions, each Work Package or Task Force Leader is free to choose their preferred online meeting platform. Meeting invitations, including links and dial-in details, will be distributed via the relevant FAIR2Adapt mailing lists by the meeting chair or Project Coordinator (PC).

3.3.4. Project website

A project website plays a crucial role in sharing information, presenting the project's vision and objectives to a wider audience. It also serves as a central resource where stakeholders and potential users can access reports, deliverables, and relevant project outcomes. The

FAIR2Adapt website (www.fair2adapt-eosc.eu) is in development and is expected to go live by Month 3 (MS7.2) of the project.

3.3.5. Project slidedeck

Anyone from the FAIR2Adapt consortium can find slides providing a general overview of the FAIR2Adapt project in the presentation slidedeck. These slides offer a concise summary of the project's objectives, goals, and key initiatives, serving as a helpful resource for understanding the scope and impact of the project. We update the presentation slidedeck regularly to ensure it reflects the latest developments and progress.

The FAIR2Adapt presentation slidedeck can be found at:

<https://w3id.org/ro-id/c8bd3371-151b-4650-9cb5-a64e40adf506/resources/d523c9ad-beea-46f9-978b-90527d3714ee>

The slides are licensed under CC-BY-4, allowing anyone to use, share, remix, and adapt them as needed.

3.3.6. Social media presence

Social media is a powerful tool for community engagement and dissemination, enabling broader outreach and fostering collaboration. It facilitates real-time interactions with diverse audiences, expanding the project's visibility and impact. Additionally, it serves as a channel for announcements and updates. FAIR2Adapt maintains an official **Bluesky account** (<https://bsky.app/profile/fair2adapt-eosc-eu.bsky.social>) and a **LinkedIn profile** (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/fair2adapt-eosc-eu>). Activity on these platforms will increase as the project website becomes fully operational.

In addition, FAIR2Adapt has a **YouTube channel** (https://www.youtube.com/@FAIR2Adapt_EU-t5t), which will host video content such as presentations, tutorials, and recorded talks, enhancing knowledge sharing and outreach.

For open-access dissemination and reporting to the European Commission, project members should use the **FAIR2Adapt Zenodo Community** (<https://zenodo.org/communities/fair2adapt>) when publishing deliverables, datasets, software, workflows, documents, presentations, and any other project-related outputs.

Alexandra Garatzogianni (Alexandra.Garatzogianni@tib.eu, TIB) is the Communication and Dissemination Lead and **Michael Fribus** (Michael.Fribus@tib.eu, TIB) is the Communication and Dissemination Deputy, They can both be contacted if a partner encounters any issues with any of these social media accounts or dissemination platforms. For further support, you can also reach out to the Project Coordinator, Anne Fouilloux (annef@simula.no).

3.3.7. Collaborative workspace

The **FAIR2Adapt project** utilizes a **shared Google Drive** hosted under **Simula's Google Workspace** for streamlined collaboration. This platform is organized with several key folders, each designed to manage and centralize different aspects of the project:

- **Contact List:** Contains the list of project partners along with their contact information.
- **Events:** Gathers records of events attended by partners, including abstracts submitted to various conferences and workshops.
- **Financial:** Stores all financial documents, including budgets, invoices, and funding-related materials.
- **Work Packages:** Each work package has its own sub-folder for storing relevant documents and deliverables. Work package folders are maintained by the Work Package Leaders.
- **GA/CA:** Contains copies of the **Grant Agreement** and **Consortium Agreement** for reference.
- **Visual Identity:** Includes logos and templates used for project-related communication.
- **Meetings:** Organizes sub-folders for each major meeting event, such as the **Kick-off Meeting, Executive Board Meetings, and General Assembly meetings.**

The [FAIR2Adapt shared Drive](#) provides an efficient way to store and manage documents, while ensuring that the materials are accessible to all project partners, with editing permissions granted to designated team members. This approach supports smooth collaboration and up-to-date documentation throughout the life of the project.

3.3.8. Helpdesk

The **FAIR2Adapt Helpdesk** provides comprehensive support to users engaging with the project's services, such as EOSC, data spaces, case study tools, and more. It offers guidance on using FAIR data, creating and exploiting FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs), and leveraging APIs (Python, R, Excel). The Helpdesk will also help improve the quality of FDO creation through direct assistance and quality checks.

For issue tracking and support, we use GitHub at github.com/FAIR2Adapt/fair2adapt-helpdesk and a dedicated mailing list (f2a-helpdesk@simula.no). The webpage fair2adapt.github.io/fair2adapt-helpdesk provides guidance for users, particularly for FAIR2Adapt Case Studies and their stakeholders.

3.3.9. Software source control (Github)

Software source control is essential for managing and evolving the code in any project. For the **FAIR2Adapt** project, we use GitHub as the primary version control system. The **FAIR2Adapt GitHub organization** (<https://github.com/FAIR2Adapt>) invites all project partners to join and create new repositories. Partners are also free to use other source control systems of their choice, provided they are open, as outlined in the proposal. This allows for a flexible and collaborative development environment where access control, workflow management, and integrations can be tailored to project needs.

3.4. Task Forces

The **FAIR2Adapt** project is establishing a series of task forces within the consortium to facilitate focused collaboration on key topics that are relevant across multiple work packages. These task forces will help bring together experts and stakeholders to address specific challenges and drive progress in critical areas. Following the project's kick-off meeting, the first two task forces are being organized as outlined below:

- **Case Study Needs Identification** – Led by **Barbara Magagna (GFF, WP5)**: this task force will focus on identifying the specific needs of each case study within WP3, WP4, and WP5. It will also consider whether cross-WP work is needed for defining the RO-Crate profiles for CCA communities or if a separate task force (e.g., FDO Governance) should be established to address this. The task force will begin after an initial understanding of the case study needs has been gathered.
- **Data & Knowledge Integration Task Force** – Led by **Markus Stocker (TIB, WP4)**: This task force will coordinate data search, discovery, integration, and synthesis services, addressing tasks in WP2, WP3, and WP4 (e.g., Task 2.4, Task 3.4, Task 4.2). It will engage with case study representatives as needed and once the task force's goals and approach are clearly defined.

We may have two additional task forces (we will rediscuss it at M6):

- **Metadata Task Force** – Led by **Raul Palma (PSNC, WP2)**: This task force will clarify Task 3.5 and address metadata-related aspects. It will start after a clearer understanding of the needs from the Case Study Needs Identification Task Force. The objective will be to map these needs to existing standards and turn them into FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs)
- **Case Study Stakeholder Strategy Task Force** – Led by **Tiago Capela Lourenço (FC.ID, WP6)**: This task force will collaborate with WP5 and WP6 to define the minimum requirements for establishing the Case Study Stakeholder Group. It will be formed

after further discussions in WP6 to determine if it is necessary based on the progress of the work.

3.5. Meetings

To maintain clear communication and efficient project management, **FAIR2Adapt** will organize a series of regular and ad-hoc meetings, each designed to address specific needs of the consortium. These meetings will vary in their structure, frequency, and intended audience, as detailed below:

1. **General Assembly (GA) Meetings:** Held at least 2 times annually, these plenary sessions are crucial for overall project oversight. Additional GA meetings may be called at any time upon request by the Project Coordinator (PC) or GA members, with at least 14 calendar days' notice. The General Assembly, which is responsible for project-wide strategic decisions, will focus on aligning the work across all work packages. These meetings will be led by the PC and conducted virtually through Zoom.
2. **Executive Board (EBM) Meetings:** These bi-weekly online calls aim to closely monitor project progress and address key administrative and technical matters with the Work Package leaders and the SRL Coordination team. The Project Board (PB) ensures that the project progresses smoothly according to the established plan. Chaired by the Project Coordinator (PC), these meetings can be scheduled on-demand when necessary. The frequency of these meetings may be adjusted if needed. Organizers will coordinate with the PC to secure a Zoom timeslot and distribute the meeting details to attendees. Unless otherwise stated, the same Zoom meeting room mentioned in Section 3.3.3 will be used.
3. **Task Force (TF) Meetings:** Each task force will hold meetings as required to support focused work on specific project topics. These meetings, coordinated by the respective task force leader, can be held as frequently as needed, with the timing adjusted according to project needs and goals.
4. **Work package (WP) Meetings:** Each WP leader is responsible for organizing meetings as needed, ensuring they occur with the appropriate frequency based on project requirements and goals.

For all meetings, the organizer is responsible for distributing the agenda in advance and following up with meeting outcomes, including action points. Meeting materials, such as presentations, minutes, and recordings, will be stored and shared through the project's Google Drive for easy access by all members.

3.6. Management procedures

3.6.1. Conflict resolution

The Code of Conduct (Annex1) applies to all day-to-day activities, including internal and external communication, both written and oral, as well as webinars and other interactions.

3.6.2. Payments

Coordinator's Role

- The Coordinator is solely responsible for handling payments to project partners.
- It must promptly inform partners of transferred amounts and maintain proper financial records.
- Project funds must be kept separate from the Coordinator's own assets (except for public bodies or when legally not required).
- No partner will receive more than its allocated grant share before the project's completion.

Payment Process

- Payments follow Article 22.1 and Article 7 of the Grant Agreement.
- Funds are distributed in instalments:
 - **75% upon receipt of pre-financing**
 - **25% upon approval of the first periodic report**
- The Coordinator distributes funds only after receiving payments from the Granting Authority.
- Payments can be withheld or recovered if a partner breaches its obligations or has not signed the Consortium Agreement.

3.6.3. Reporting

Official Reporting to the EC for the FAIR2Adapt project are as follows:

- Period 1: M1 - M18
 - Periodic report to be submitted within 60 days (M20 - end of August 2026)
- Period 2: M19 - M36
 - Periodic and final report to be submitted within 60 days (M38 - end of February 2028)

Internal status and progress reports are essential to keep track of costs and resource spending. This will help us discover if any partners are struggling to meet their deadlines, deliverables, budgets or person month estimates and can help us correct errors before we report to the commission.

Financial reports should be done in the template provided by the CO.

Internal technical reports should be done in the interim report template.

Partners are expected to report any deviations to the plans, both budget and technical and also comment on executed work and risks.

Internal reports will be reviewed by the coordinating group and discussed in the status meetings.

The Parties commit to continuously provide information on the progress of the implementation of the task assigned to them in the Grant Agreement.

The coordinator will request internal reports in connection with the General Assemblies, every 6 months, and can request additional relevant implementation information from one or more partners when reasonable.

3.6.4. Knowledge management strategy and IPR

For the success of the FAIR2Adapt project, consortium partners are expected to generate new knowledge, some of which may be eligible for intellectual property (IP) protection. At the same time, they have a responsibility to share newly developed methods and tools. To balance open access dissemination with safeguarding partner IP rights, a structured knowledge management strategy must be established. This strategy will adhere to the guidelines outlined in the Model Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA). The key principles governing IP management include:

- **Ownership of Results:** Each partner owns the results they generate.
- **Joint Ownership:** If results are jointly owned, each owner can exploit and license them independently unless otherwise agreed. Protection measures and cost-sharing must be pre-agreed.
- **Transfer of Results:** Partners can transfer ownership of their results (including joint results) following the Grant Agreement. Identified third-party transfers are pre-approved unless modified by the General Assembly. Transfers must not affect other partners' rights.

- **Mergers & Acquisitions:** If a partner undergoes a merger or acquisition, prior notice may not always be possible, but obligations apply as long as other partners have access rights.
- **Knowledge Management & IP Strategy:** The project aims to generate and protect new knowledge while ensuring open dissemination. IP management aligns with the Grant and Consortium Agreements, balancing open access with partner rights.

3.6.5. Data and Innovation Management

The FAIR2Adapt project will utilize data from various providers in accordance with their respective data access policies and will generate refined datasets and research outputs based on selected case studies and derived use cases. Additionally, it will access metadata from resource providers and create supplementary metadata and annotations. Data governance policies will be outlined and continuously updated in the FAIR2Adapt project's Data Management Plan. The key principles are as follows:

- **Input Data:** Access and usage will strictly adhere to the policies set by the original data providers. The project will implement safeguards to prevent misuse, ensuring that, when required, only authorized partners can access both the data and related infrastructures.
- **Processed Data:** Refined datasets will be shared with project partners and selected external communities for evaluation. In some cases, representative portions of the processed data will be made publicly available through communication and dissemination channels. The project infrastructure will support storage and long-term preservation, with the possibility of utilizing EOSC services.
- **Metadata and Annotations:** Metadata made publicly available by resource providers will be accessed and harvested without modification. However, the **FAIR2Adapt** project will generate additional annotations to enhance resource metadata where necessary. Both the original metadata and the added annotations will be openly shared, with clear attribution to the respective sources and contributors.

Furthermore, innovation management will oversee project activities that drive knowledge application and uptake. These efforts will be guided by the project's intellectual property strategy and closely linked to networking, exploitation, and business planning activities.

4. Quality assurance and Risk Management

4.1. Quality assurance

Quality assurance encompasses all activities necessary to ensure that the Grant Agreement is implemented effectively and meets the expected quality standards. To maintain continuous and rigorous oversight, the FAIR2Adapt Coordinator oversees overall technical coordination and management. The Coordinator is responsible for defining the project’s technological and development strategy, facilitating collaboration among work package leaders and task leaders, ensuring that technical milestones are achieved, and overseeing the timely submission of deliverables and internal reports. Additionally, the Coordinator works closely with document reviewers to uphold technical quality.

The **Deliverable Leader** is responsible for managing the review process, seeking and appointing appropriate reviewers from within the consortium, and ensuring that deliverables undergo thorough assessment before submission. The deliverable development process follows a structured timeline:

- **~60 days before submission:** An initial outline (e.g., draft Table of Contents) is created using the project’s deliverable template and the internal reviewers are appointed.
- **~15 days before submission:** Partners submit their finalized, high-quality contributions.
- **~10 days before submission:** The deliverable leader compiles the candidate version and submits it to the assigned reviewer for evaluation.
- **~5 days before submission:** Reviewers provide feedback, and if necessary, the deliverable leader, in collaboration with relevant partners, revises and finalizes the document.

Table 3 List of Deliverables

No	Deliverable Name & Short description	WP	Lead	Type	Dissemination level	Due
D1.1	Project Handbook: document 1) the quality control processes; 2) risks and their corresponding mitigation plans; 3) ethics & compliance issues; and 4) planned governance structure, roles, and responsibilities, including the external advisory board and the resources (technical documents, meeting platforms, frequency and modality of meetings, etc.) they will have.	WP1	SRL	R	PU	M3
D1.2	Data Management Plan: it will evolve during the lifetime of the project in order to present the status of the project's reflections on data management. Our	WP1	SRL	DMP	PU	M6

D1.1 – Project Handbook

	DMP will be made publicly available on ROHub so that the up to date version can be consulted at any time by everyone.					
D1.3	First Project activity, including Governance report: admin, technical, governance, risks and ethics project activities, including board meetings, decisions taken, and the implications of those decisions on the project.	WP1	SRL	R	PU	M12
D1.4	Intermediate Project activity report, including Evaluation on Governance Impact: similar to D1.3 but project activities in Year 2.	WP1	SRL	R	PU	M24
D1.5	Final Project activity report, including Evaluation on Governance Impact: report all the project activities, with an emphasis with Year 3, and includes a comprehensive report evaluating the effectiveness of the governance structure across the project’s lifespan and lessons learned.	WP1	SRL	R	PU	M36
D1.6	First Policy Briefing: Provide insights and recommendations to inform policy developments and support inter-project learning through a concise Policy Briefing deliverable.	WP1	SRL	R	PU	M18
D1.7	Final Policy Briefing: Summarise and present final insights and recommendations to inform policy developments and support inter-project learning through a comprehensive Policy Briefing deliverable.	WP1	SRL	R	PU	M36
D2.1	FDO service integration in ROHub - version 1: all the available services are integrated into ROHub.	WP2	PSNC	O	PU	M21
D2.2	FDO service integration in ROHub - final version : final version of all the available services are integrated in ROHub	WP2	PSNC	O	PU	M33
D3.1	FAIRification framework: conceptual and technical framework, including a methodology for FAIRification of CCA DOs, FIPs and the extension of RO-Crate profiles to extend them in support of climate adaptation scenarios.	WP3	UPM	R	PU	M12
D3.2	FAIRification services: deliverable describing the FAIRification services including 1) the FAIR assessment service, based on CCA best practices and FIPs, and using the metadata extraction services proposed in Task 3.2; 2) the service to automatically align dataset variables to I-ADOPT, based on Task 3.3; 3) knowledge extraction, production and metadata enrichment services based on Task 3.4; and 4) the FAIR data publishing pipeline described in Task 3.5.	WP3	UPM	R	PU	M18
D3.3	FAIRification services adapted to CCA: all services are released an integrated in the ROHub platform as in order to aid FDO FAIRification	WP3	UPM	O	PU	M36
D4.1	Knowledge Services specifications: Report detailing the technical specifications that translate the user requirements (Task 5.2) into system specifications for Knowledge Services.	WP4	TIB	R	PU	M24

D4.2	Knowledge Services for climate change adaptation: Knowledge Services released as an ecosystem of production services and software releases on Github and Zenodo.	WP4	TIB	O	PU	M36
D5.1	Community Capacity Building Report: detail the provided training sessions, workshops, and webinars enhancing community capabilities and understanding of FAIR principles, including statistics on trainees and participation feedback.	WP5	GFF	R	PU	M24
D5.2	User Requirements Report: summarise the specific user requirement analysis for the case studies, including the method used to ensure continuous adjustments and adaptations are made based on evolving stakeholder needs.	WP5	GFF	R	PU	M12
D5.3	1st release of the Customised CCA-related Services: First release of the tailored services developed, with the corresponding documentation detailing functionalities, usage, and applicable scenarios. The documentation will also include short online tutorials to ensure clear, user-friendly access to services.	WP5	SRL	O	PU	M18
D5.4	Final release of customised CCA-related Services: Final release of the tailored services developed, with the corresponding documentation detailing functionalities, usage, and applicable scenarios. The documentation will also include online tutorials to ensure clear, user-friendly access to services.	WP5	SRL	O	PU	M36
D6.1	Stocktaking report on adaptation data and knowledge needs: Detailed report for each of the case studies, including the review of adaptation knowledge needs, stakeholder engagement plans, methods, expected outcomes, timelines, and expected synergies between the case studies and the external initiatives or projects (e.g., RiOMar, weADAPT, national or local adaptation process).	WP6	SEI	R	PU	M12
D6.2	Proof-of-concept of the FAIR2Adapt services supporting the creation of FDOs: Six proof-of-concept applications of the FAIR2Adapt services supporting the creation of FDOs.	WP6	FC.ID	R	PU	M36
D6.3	Report on the uptake via the EU Mission and EOSC: Report on the engagement activities that were carried out, including identification of main challenges, opportunities and necessary actors for successful future dissemination and uptake of FAIR2Adapt resources by the EU Mission signatories and EOSC partnership members.	WP6	FTC	R	PU	M36
D7.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan: detail the strategic plan for targeted engagement, outreach, exploitation, and communication activities.	WP7	TIB	R	PU	M6
D7.2	First Dissemination, communication and cooperation with EOSC & mission adaptation activities: updated dissemination & communication plan & activities, as well as detailed report on the engagement activities	WP7	TIB	R	PU	M24

	with EOSC and mission adaptation and their outcomes.					
D7.3	Final Dissemination, communication and cooperation with EOSC & mission adaptation activities: Overview of the activities performed and outcomes of these activities, including shared experiences, results, and lessons learned from collaborating with EOSC and the EU Mission adaptation.	WP7	TIB	R	PU	M36
D7.4	Business Plan and Exploitation Strategy Issue 1: preliminary insights on target user communities/domain(s)/market(s) and on the competitive environment, viability and liability analysis and risk analysis.	WP7	ALPHA	R	SEN	M18
D7.5	Business Plan and Exploitation Strategy Issue 2: final findings on all the exploitation actions aimed to support and adopt and present business opportunities within and outside the EOSC community and portal.	WP7	ALPHA	R	SEN	M36

4.2. Ethics & Compliance Issues in the FAIR2Adapt Project

The FAIR2Adapt project is committed to upholding the highest standards of ethics, integrity, and compliance. Given the project’s focus on FAIR data principles, climate change adaptation, and collaboration across various stakeholders, it is essential to proactively address ethical considerations and ensure compliance with legal and regulatory frameworks. This section outlines key ethical and compliance issues relevant to FAIR2Adapt and provides guidelines for managing them effectively.

4.2.1. Data Privacy and Protection

FAIR2Adapt processes and integrates diverse datasets, some of which may contain sensitive environmental, socio-economic, or personal information. Compliance with **data protection regulations**, such as the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**, is mandatory. The project will:

- Ensure **data anonymization and de-identification** where necessary.
- Obtain **informed consent** from individuals if personal data is used.
- Implement **secure data storage and transfer** mechanisms.
- Follow best practices for **open data sharing** while respecting privacy constraints.
- Regularly audit data handling processes to ensure compliance.

4.2.2. Ethical Data Use and FAIR Principles

The project promotes **responsible and ethical data sharing** while aligning with the **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles**. Ethical data use involves:

- Ensuring **transparency and accountability** in data collection, processing, and sharing.
- Avoiding **misuse or misinterpretation** of data, particularly in policy and decision-making contexts.
- Addressing potential **biases in data sources** to ensure fair representation and inclusion.
- Encouraging data provenance tracking to maintain trust and reproducibility.

4.2.3. Ethical Research and Stakeholder Engagement

FAIR2Adapt engages a broad range of stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, industry representatives, and local communities. Ethical considerations include:

- **Respect for indigenous and local knowledge systems**, ensuring equitable collaboration.
- Avoiding **conflicts of interest** by maintaining transparency in partnerships and funding.
- Encouraging **inclusive participation**, ensuring that all voices, especially underrepresented groups, are heard and considered.
- Adhering to established **codes of conduct** for ethical research collaborations.

4.2.4. Compliance with European and International Standards

FAIR2Adapt operates within the framework of European and international policies, including:

- **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)** guidelines on data sharing, open science, and interoperability.
- **Mission Adaptation** and **EU Green Deal** compliance for climate-related initiatives.
- Alignment with **United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**, particularly on climate action, responsible consumption, and partnerships.
- Ethical guidelines provided by the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#).

4.2.5. Risk Management in Ethics & Compliance

To proactively manage ethical and compliance risks, the project will:

- Maintain an **Ethics and Compliance Register** to track and address emerging ethical concerns.
- Conduct **regular ethics reviews** as part of project governance.
- Ensure that all partners undergo **ethics and compliance training** at the project's outset and throughout its lifecycle.

4.2.6. Addressing Ethical Issues and Reporting Mechanisms

Any ethical concerns or compliance violations must be reported immediately. FAIR2Adapt establishes the following mechanisms:

- A **confidential reporting system** to address ethical concerns.
- Designation of an **Ethics Officer** responsible for handling compliance issues.
- Regular ethics training sessions to keep all project members informed of best practices.
- A structured **review process for reported issues**, ensuring transparency and accountability in resolution.

4.3. Risk Management

4.3.1. Risk Management Methodology

Effective risk management is critical to the success of the FAIR2Adapt project. Given its complexity and the interdisciplinary nature of its objectives, a structured and proactive risk management approach is adopted. This methodology ensures that potential risks are identified, assessed, and mitigated in a timely manner, minimizing their impact on project deliverables, timelines, and resources. The risk management strategy follows established best practices and consists of the following key phases:

1. **Establishing Context**

The first step in risk management is defining the internal and external factors that may influence the project's ability to meet its objectives. This includes:

- Understanding the regulatory, technical, and operational environment.
- Identifying key stakeholders and their risk tolerance.
- Assessing dependencies on external data sources, infrastructures, and collaborations.

2. Risk Identification and Assessment

Potential risks are systematically identified through structured discussions at both the project and work package levels. This phase includes:

- Internal brainstorming sessions with project partners.
- Reviewing past experiences from similar projects.
- Identifying risks related to data access, interoperability, funding, technological adoption, and ethical issues.
- Classifying risks based on their likelihood and potential impact.

3. Qualitative Risk Analysis

Each identified risk is analyzed in terms of:

- **Likelihood:** The probability of the risk occurring (high, medium, or low).
- **Impact:** The effect on project performance, costs, or timeline if the risk materializes (high, medium, or low).
- **Interactions:** How different risks may be interrelated and compound project challenges.

4. Risk Response Planning

Appropriate strategies are developed to mitigate identified risks. Response measures include:

- **Avoidance:** Modifying plans to eliminate the risk.
- **Mitigation:** Implementing proactive steps to reduce risk likelihood or impact.
- **Transfer:** Assigning responsibility to external parties when applicable.
- **Acceptance:** Recognizing that some risks must be tolerated while preparing contingency plans.

5. Risk Monitoring and Control

Risk management is a continuous process throughout the project lifecycle. Monitoring activities include:

- Regular risk assessment updates during project meetings.
- Tracking key risks and their mitigation measures.
- Implementing a risk register to document and monitor risks.
- Reassessing risks in response to project developments or external changes.

6. Roles and Responsibilities

- **Project Coordinator:** Ensures risk management is integrated into overall project governance and the quality process management, overseeing the risk register and ensuring project continuity.
- **Work Package Leaders:** Identify and assess risks within their respective domains.
- **Risk Manager (or Assigned Responsible Party):** Oversees risk management implementation, ensures corrective actions are taken when necessary, and chairs regular risk assessment sessions during Executive Board Meetings (EBMs).
- **All Partners:** Contribute to risk identification, analysis, and mitigation as part of their project activities.

By adopting this structured approach, the FAIR2Adapt project aims to proactively address challenges, ensuring a resilient and adaptive project execution that aligns with its goals and FAIR principles. Furthermore, risk management is integrated with quality control processes to ensure project results, milestones, and deliverables undergo a quality review prior to submission to the EC, while ethical issues are actively managed by the Project Management Office (SRL Coordination Team and the Work Package Leaders).

4.3.2. Initial Risk Analysis

Table 4 Table of Risks

Description of Risk	Likelihood	Impact	WPs	Mitigation Strategy Overview
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Failure to integrate and maintain the Core FDO Infrastructure	High	High	WP2, WP1	Ensure early-stage development of interoperable standards, ongoing testing, and periodic reviews.
Insufficient stakeholder engagement and buy-in for FAIRification processes	Medium	High	WP3, WP5	Engage stakeholders early in co-design, provide targeted training, and continuous feedback loops.
Challenges in standardizing data formats (DTR, RO-Crate, etc.)	High	Medium	WP2, WP3	Reuse existing standards as much as possible and collaborate with external standards organizations.
Inadequate user-centric services or tools for CCA communities	Medium	High	WP4, WP5	Conduct regular user needs assessments, collaborate closely with end-users, and iterate on feedback.
Data privacy and security concerns during FAIRification of CCA data	High	High	WP2, WP7	Implement strict data protection protocols, ensure GDPR compliance, and regularly audit practices.
Lack of capacity building and training for stakeholders	Medium	Medium	WP5, WP4	Develop comprehensive training programs and offer multiple modes of delivery (webinars, workshops, etc.).
Difficulty in testing and validating frameworks through real-world case studies	Medium	Medium	WP6	Set clear case study objectives, establish iterative feedback processes, and address any gaps quickly.
Poor dissemination of project results leading to limited engagement or uptake	Medium	Medium	WP7	Develop a robust dissemination strategy, engage with external communication experts, and actively engage with stakeholders.

Inconsistent quality control and monitoring of project deliverables	High	High	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4	Implement an integrated quality assurance system, assign quality champions within each WP.
Insufficient collaboration with EOSC, Mission Adaptation, or related initiatives	Low	Medium	WP7	Establish early communication channels, integrate with EOSC goals, and align with mission objectives.
Failure to meet technical milestones or project timelines	High	High	WP1, WP2, WP6	Regular progress reviews, set realistic deadlines, and allocate additional resources where necessary.
Budget overruns due to unforeseen technical or administrative issues	Medium	Medium	WP1, WP2	Conduct frequent budget audits, maintain contingency funds, and ensure transparent financial reporting.
Resistance to adopting new services or tools by end-users	Medium	Medium	WP4, WP5	Engage end-users early in the co-design process, provide targeted demonstrations and ease of use.
Difficulty in sustaining project results and services beyond the project lifecycle	Medium	High	WP7	Develop a sustainability plan early in the project, including potential funding sources and partnerships.
Ethical issues related to data use or user involvement	Low	High	WP2, WP5, WP7	Ensure compliance with ethical guidelines, establish a review committee, and provide ethical training.
Lack of coordination leading to delayed or incomplete user requirement delivery	Medium	High	WP2, WP3	Create a cross-WP task force to ensure alignment of user requirements, foster regular communication across WPs, and set clear deadlines for deliverables.

<p>Difficulty in aligning cross-WP efforts leading to delays in delivering user-centric services</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>WP2, WP3, WP4</p>	<p>Establish clear coordination channels and regular cross-WP meetings to track progress and address</p>
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5. Annex

5.1. Code of Conduct (COC)

5.1.1. Purpose and Scope

The Code of Conduct defines the ethical principles, professional behavior, and collaboration standards to which all Members of the consortium must adhere to ensure a respectful, inclusive, and productive working environment.

5.1.2. Principles

All Parties shall:

- Act with the highest standards of integrity, respect, and fairness, setting an example for ethical and professional behavior at all times.
- Ensure all communication is open, honest, and transparent, strictly adhering to respectful, inclusive, and professional language in every interaction.
- Create and actively maintain an inclusive and equitable environment, where diversity is celebrated, and discrimination of any kind is unequivocally rejected.
- Firmly reject and report any form of harassment, bullying, intimidation, or inappropriate behavior, holding ourselves and others accountable.

5.1.3. Application and Enforcement

The Code of Conduct applies to all FAIR2Adapt project activities, both online and in person. Any member observing or experiencing a breach of this Code of Conduct may report it to the Project Coordinator, who shall ensure that the matter is addressed promptly and confidentially. Severe or repeated violations may be escalated to the General Assembly for

resolution, with potential consequences including removal from governance roles or other appropriate actions in accordance with Section 7.3.7.

5.1.4. Communication and Review

The Code of Conduct shall be shared with all Members and Associated Partners of the consortium upon their accession to the Consortium Agreement.

The General Assembly shall review the Code of Conduct periodically and make updates as necessary to align with evolving project needs and ethical considerations.